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RESEARCH PAPER

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC AND OBSTETRIC RISK FACTORS FOR UTERINE RUPTURE: A FIVE-YEAR CASE-CONTROL STUDY IN A NIGERIAN TERTIARY HOSPITAL

Tiamiyu I¹, Ogbiti M.I.², Ibrahim H.I.¹, Dawúd R.M.¹, Nwankwo C.C.³, Ezugwu O.P.¹, Ojeh-Oziegbe O.G.⁴
Abubakar S.M.¹, Balogun S.A.¹, Bathna D.¹, Calvin C.¹, Habibah I.I.¹, Nakande J.A.¹, Abdulraheem M.¹, Ja'afaru U.¹

¹Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi State.

²Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital, Irrua, Edo State.

³Department of Chemical Pathology, Faculty of Basic Clinical Sciences, Ambrose Alli University.

⁴Department of Radiation Oncology, Oncoclinics Africa, Benin City, Edo State.

Correspondence: tiamiyuismail21@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Uterine rupture remains a catastrophic complication in low- and middle-income countries like Nigeria. This study identified risk factors for uterine rupture among 91 cases and 400 controls in a Nigerian tertiary hospital. Increased risks were found for lower socioeconomic status (Odds Ratio [OR] = 3.64, $p = 0.015$) and unbooked status (OR = 11.3, $p < 0.001$). Obstetric factors with significant associations included high parity (≥ 5 : OR = 5.7, $p < 0.001$), previous cesarean section (OR = 2.6, $p < 0.001$), use of oxytocics (OR = 8.2, $p < 0.001$), and prolonged obstructed labor (OR = 41.6, $p < 0.001$). In the multivariable model, previous cesarean section (Adjusted OR [AOR] = 16.6, $p < 0.001$), use of oxytocics (AOR = 17.6, $p < 0.001$), and prolonged obstructed labor (AOR = 10.65, $p < 0.001$) were significant independent risk factors. High parity (≥ 5 : AOR = 5.4, $p = 0.021$) was also a risk factor, while younger age (≤ 20 years: AOR = 0.15, $p = 0.023$) was protective. The study shows the need to improve antenatal care and emergency obstetric services. A key limitation is the retrospective nature of this single-center study, which is susceptible to incomplete data and potential selection bias.

Keywords: Antenatal care, Cesarean section, Parity, Risk factors, Uterine rupture

INTRODUCTION

Uterine rupture is a rare but catastrophic obstetric complication that poses significant risks to maternal and perinatal health, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). It occurs when the uterine wall tears during pregnancy or labor, often leading to severe hemorrhage, fetal distress, and maternal mortality if not promptly managed. (Liao *et al.*, 2023) The incidence of uterine rupture in high-income countries is typically low, with studies estimating an occurrence of approximately 0.012% of deliveries for unscarred uteri. (Gerard and Nahum, 2016) However, in LMICs, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, the incidence is considerably higher, with some reports indicating rates as high as 1 to 3% of all deliveries. (Diallo *et al.*, 1998; Adanu and Obed, 2001).

Sub-Saharan Africa bears a significant burden of maternal morbidity and mortality, with an estimated maternal mortality ratio of 512 deaths per 100,000 live births in Nigeria, one of the highest in the world. (Oweibia *et al.*, 2025) The high incidence of uterine rupture in this context is linked to factors such as poor access to emergency obstetric care, delayed medical intervention, and socio-economic barriers to seeking timely and appropriate treatment. (Assefa and Wesson, 2019; Kenea, Fikru Biyana and Marine, 2025) In Nigeria, studies have shown that uterine rupture accounts for a considerable proportion of maternal deaths, particularly in areas with underdeveloped healthcare infrastructure. (Etuk *et al.*, 2019; Jombo *et al.*, 2022).

Socio-demographic factors, such as maternal age, education level, and socio-economic status, play a pivotal role. Women from lower socio-economic backgrounds are at greater risk, as they are less likely to access proper antenatal care and more likely to experience prolonged labor and obstructed deliveries. (Cavazos-Rehg *et al.*, 2015; Kim *et al.*, 2018).

Obstetric factors are equally critical in understanding the risk of uterine rupture. High parity, or multiple previous pregnancies, increases the mechanical stress on the uterus. (Hofmeyr, Say and Gülmezoglu, 2005; Wan *et al.*, 2022) Women with previous cesarean sections are at a significantly increased risk of rupture in subsequent pregnancies due to the weakened uterine scar. (Arusi *et al.*, 2023) The improper use of oxytocic drugs to induce or augment labor also contributes to the risk of uterine rupture. (Al-Zirqi *et al.*, 2017).

Uterine rupture remains a significant challenge, accounting for up to 16% of maternal deaths in some Nigerian tertiary hospitals, with the majority of cases occurring in women who are unbooked for antenatal care. (Etuk *et al.*, 2019; Abdulfattah Mohammed *et al.*, 2023) The interaction of these risk factors shows the need for targeted interventions, including enhancing access to skilled obstetric care and promoting timely and appropriate use of cesarean sections.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design: This was a case-control study conducted over a period of five years at a tertiary hospital in Bauchi, Nigeria. The objective was to identify the socio-demographic and obstetric risk factors associated with uterine rupture. A total of 91 women who experienced uterine rupture (cases) were compared with 400 randomly selected controls from the general obstetric population who had deliveries during the same time frame.

Study Population and Selection Criteria: Cases were women diagnosed with uterine rupture based on clinical findings and surgical records from the hospital's obstetric unit. The control group consisted of women who delivered at the hospital during the same period and did not have uterine rupture. Controls were selected using systematic random sampling from the delivery register in the labor ward, and not pure random sampling. Women were excluded from the study if they had incomplete data or refused consent. Controls with other obstetric complications were retained in the study to accurately represent the general obstetric population at risk of uterine rupture. Women were excluded from the study if they had incomplete data or if they refused to provide consent. Furthermore, women with obstetric complications unrelated to uterine rupture were also excluded to ensure the focus remained on factors directly associated with uterine rupture.

Data Collection: Data were extracted from hospital records, including labor ward records, theatre records, and departmental obstetric data sheets. A pre-tested case report form (CRF) was used for data collection by trained research assistants to ensure consistency and accuracy. Data collected included socio-demographic factors, such as maternal age, education level, and husband's occupation, and obstetric factors, such as parity, booking status, previous uterine scars, occurrence of prolonged obstructed labor, and use of oxytocics.

Operational Definitions: Social Class: Determined based on maternal educational level and husband's occupation, using the modified Oyediji classification system. (Ibadin and Akpede, 2021)

- **Unbooked Status:** Defined as a patient who did not have at least one antenatal care visit at the study hospital or its affiliated centers during the current pregnancy.
- **High Parity:** Defined as having five or more previous pregnancies (Parity ≥ 5).
- **Prolonged Obstructed Labor:** Defined clinically as a labor that has stopped progressing despite adequate uterine contractions.
- **Use of Oxytocics:** Defined as the administration of oxytocin, prostaglandins, or other labor-inducing agents for induction or augmentation of labor in the current delivery.

Data Analysis: Data were entered into and analyzed using SPSS software for Windows version 26.0. Descriptive statistics were calculated, and results were presented in tables. The Chi-square test was used to assess significant differences between proportions ($p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant). The odds ratio (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated. For handling missing data, only cases with complete data for all variables in the final multivariable model were included in that specific analysis.

Multivariable Analysis: Variables found to be significant in the univariable analysis were included in a multivariable logistic regression model to identify independent risk factors. The potential for instability in the multivariable model, suggested by wide confidence intervals in preliminary analysis, was noted, and the interpretation of Adjusted ORs focused only on factors with robust statistical significance. Standard methods for case-control studies were employed.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the institution. All participants provided written informed consent before their inclusion in the study, and data were anonymized to ensure confidentiality.

RESULTS

Socio-Demographic Risk Factors for Ruptured Uterus (Table 1)

Women aged ≤ 20 years had a significantly lower risk of uterine rupture (OR = 0.2, 95% CI: 0.056–0.437, $p < 0.001$). Socioeconomic status was a significant factor, with women from the lower socioeconomic class showing a higher risk (OR = 3.64, 95% CI: 1.10–12.08, $p = 0.015$). Education level did not show a significant association ($p = 0.315$). Unbooked status was strongly associated with uterine rupture (OR = 11.3, 95% CI: 3.00–46.90, $p < 0.001$).

Obstetric Risk Factors for Uterine Rupture (Table 2)

High parity (≥ 5 pregnancies) was a significant risk factor (OR = 5.7, 95% CI: 3.49–9.18, $p < 0.001$). Previous cesarean section was a strong risk factor (OR = 2.6, 95% CI: 1.53–4.49, $p < 0.001$). The use of oxytocics was significantly associated with increased risk (OR = 8.2, 95% CI: 5.19–15.00, $p < 0.001$). Prolonged obstructed labor had the highest association (OR = 41.6, 95% CI: 20.18–85.83, $p < 0.001$).

Multivariable Logistic Model for Ruptured Uterus (Table 3)

Following adjustment for potential confounders in the multivariable logistic model, several independent risk factors for uterine rupture were identified. Age ≤ 20 years was found to be significantly protective (Adjusted Odds Ratio [AOR] = 0.15, $p = 0.023$). Unbooked status was no longer statistically significant in this final model (AOR = 12.5, $p = 0.650$). The variables that remained significant independent risk factors were: Previous Cesarean Section (AOR = 16.6, 95% CI: 4.643–22.915, $p < 0.001$), Use of Oxytocics (AOR = 17.6, 95% CI: 3.832–20.280, $p < 0.001$), Prolonged Obstructed Labor (AOR = 10.65, 95% CI: 4.510–21.826, $p < 0.001$), and High Parity (Age ≥ 5 : AOR = 5.4, 95% CI: 1.200–12.900, $p = 0.021$).

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Risk Factors for Ruptured Uterus among Study Participants

Variable	Cases n=91 (%)	Controls n=400 (%)	Odds-ratio (OR)	Confidence Interval (CI)	P-value
Age (years)					
≤20	4 (4.4)	91 (22.8)	0.2	0.056 – 0.437	<0.001
21–40	84 (92.3)	295 (73.8)	3.5	0.373 – 4.733	0.660
>40	3 (3.3)	14 (3.5)	1	–	–
Socioeconomic Status					
Upper Class	3 (3.3)	41 (10.3)	1.0	–	–
Middle Class	11 (12.1)	70 (17.5)	2.15	0.57 – 8.15	0.127
Lower Class	77 (84.6)	289 (72.3)	3.64	1.10 – 12.08	0.015
Lack of Formal Education	60 (65.9)	241 (60.3)	1.30	0.90 – 2.10	0.315
Unbooked Status	89 (97.8)	319 (79.8)	11.30	3.00 – 46.90	<0.001

Figure 1: Age distribution of cases

Table 2: Obstetric risk factors for uterine rupture among study participants.

Variable	Subjects N=91 (%)	Controls N=400 (%)	Odds Ratio (OR)	Confidence Interval	p – value
Parity					
0	1 (1.1)	75 (18.8)	1	–	–
1 – 4	34 (37.4)	237 (59.2)	0.2	0.140 – 1.370	0.083
>4	56 (61.5)	88 (22.0)	5.7	3.490 – 9.180	<0.001
Previous caesarean section	26 (28.6)	53 (13.3)	2.6	1.528 – 4.489	<0.001
Use of oxytocic	44 (48.4)	36 (9)	8.2	5.190 – 15.002	<0.001
Prolonged obstructed labour	51 (56.0)	11 (2.8)	41.6	20.182 – 85.827	<0.001

Table 3: Multivariable logistic model for ruptured uterus.

Independent Risk Factors	Adjusted Or	CI	P-Value
Age ≤20 years	0.15	0.005 – 0.600	0.023
Unbooked status	12.5	9.212 – 18.416	0.650
Parity ≥5	5.4	1.200 – 12.900	0.021
Previous Caesarean section	16.6	4.643 – 22.915	<0.001
Use of oxytocics	17.6	3.832 – 20.280	<0.001
Prolonged obstructed labour	10.650	4.510 – 21.826	<0.001

DISCUSSION

The findings of this case-control study highlight several critical socio-demographic and obstetric risk factors for uterine rupture in a Nigerian tertiary hospital setting. Women under the age of 20 had a significantly lower risk of uterine rupture (OR = 0.2, $p < 0.001$), a finding consistent with a study done by Nonye-Enyidah *et al.*, (2025) This suggests that younger women may have stronger uterine tissue and fewer cumulative obstetric risk factors, such as high parity or previous scars, compared to older women.

Women from lower socioeconomic backgrounds showed a significantly higher risk (OR = 3.64, $p = 0.015$). This may be attributed to reduced access to quality healthcare, delayed presentation, and financial constraints.(Ohonsi and Attah, 2011; Pipal *et al.*, 2025) Consistent with this, unbooked status showed a strong univariable association (OR = 11.3, $p < 0.001$), confirming its role as a major barrier to timely screening and intervention.(Ahmed, Mengistu and Endalamaw, 2018; Ojuronbe *et al.*, 2023) While unbooked status was not statistically significant in the multivariable model, the strong univariable association suggests it acts as a proxy for the socioeconomic and systemic factors that delay access to care.

High parity (≥ 5) was identified as a significant independent risk factor (AOR = 5.4, $p = 0.021$). Previous cesarean section also emerged as a powerful independent risk factor (AOR = 16.6, $p < 0.001$), consistent with the known

cumulative strain on the uterus and the inherent weakness of the uterine scar.(Kumara, Debelew and Ademe, 2024) These results emphasize the need for careful management and counseling in high-parity women and those attempting a trial of labor after a previous cesarean section.

Prolonged obstructed labor was the strongest risk factor in the univariable analysis (OR = 41.6, $p < 0.001$) and remained a significant independent factor (AOR = 10.65, $p < 0.001$). This result aligns with findings that delayed intervention during obstructed labor is a leading cause of rupture.(Namagembe *et al.*, 2022) Similarly, the use of oxytocics was strongly associated with rupture (AOR = 17.6, $p < 0.001$). Given the retrospective nature of the study, it is important to note that the high adjusted odds ratios for previous cesarean section, oxytocics, and obstructed labor should be interpreted cautiously, as they may be subject to overestimation due to potential model instability. These findings, nonetheless, reinforce the critical need for strict protocols governing the use of labor augmentation agents and timely access to emergency cesarean delivery.

Women under the age of 20 had a significantly lower risk of uterine rupture, as reflected in the odds ratio (OR = 0.2, $p < 0.001$). This finding aligns with similar studies conducted in Rivers state by.Nonye-Enyidah *et al.*, (2025), which also reported lower complication rates in younger women. This pattern could be explained by biological factors, where younger women tend to have stronger uterine tissue and fewer pre-existing complications, such as prior cesarean sections or high parity. This result is critical in the context of maternal health, as it highlights the need to focus on other risk factors like high parity and obstetric care in older women. Given that younger women are at a lower risk of uterine rupture, interventions should be aimed at improving antenatal care for women at higher risk, particularly those above 40 or with multiple pregnancies.

Women from lower socioeconomic backgrounds showed a significantly higher risk of uterine rupture (OR = 3.64, $p = 0.015$), a result consistent with studies by Ohonsi and Attah, (2011) in Kano, Nigeria and Pipal *et al.*, (2025) in India. This can be attributed to barriers to accessing quality healthcare, such as financial constraints, poor nutrition, and lack of education. Lower socioeconomic status often leads to inadequate prenatal care, including the lack of early detection of complications like uterine rupture. This finding emphasizes the importance of addressing socioeconomic disparities in maternal health. Public health initiatives should focus on improving access to affordable antenatal care for women from low-income communities to prevent complications and improve maternal outcomes.

Unbooked status was strongly associated with uterine rupture (OR = 11.3, $p < 0.001$), confirming the results from Ahmed, Mengistu and Endalamaw (2018) in Ethiopia and Ojurongbe *et al.*, (2023) in Nasarawa, Nigeria, which linked unbooked pregnancies to increased maternal risk. The lack of formal antenatal care means that women miss out on early screening, health education, and timely interventions. The absence of regular prenatal visits may also contribute to the late diagnosis of uterine rupture during labor, leading to poor outcomes. The public health significance of this finding is clear: increasing the coverage and accessibility of antenatal care services, particularly in rural and underserved areas, should be prioritized to reduce maternal morbidity and mortality.

High parity and previous cesarean section were found to be significant risk factors for uterine rupture. This is consistent with findings from a study by Kumara, Debelew and Ademe (2024) in Ethiopia who observed higher rupture rates in women with multiple pregnancies and uterine scars. The increased risk associated with high parity could be due to the cumulative strain on the uterus, whereas previous cesarean sections increase the likelihood of rupture due to weakened uterine walls. These findings highlight the importance of monitoring pregnancies with multiple risk factors, particularly in women with a history of cesarean sections. Clinical guidelines should emphasize the careful management of high-parity pregnancies and the counseling of women with previous cesarean sections regarding the risks of uterine rupture in subsequent pregnancies.

Prolonged obstructed labor was the most significant risk factor for uterine rupture, with an OR of 41.6 ($p < 0.001$). This result aligns with studies like those of Namagembe *et al.*, (2022) in Uganda, which found that delayed intervention during obstructed labor was the leading risk of uterine rupture. Prolonged labor exerts significant pressure on the uterus,

making it more susceptible to rupture, particularly in the absence of timely intervention such as cesarean delivery. This finding calls for improved management protocols in labor, including timely cesarean sections and better access to emergency obstetric care. Policymakers should prioritize strengthening emergency obstetric care, particularly in regions with high rates of obstructed labor.

CONCLUSION

This case-control study identifies key socio-demographic and obstetric factors associated with uterine rupture in a Nigerian tertiary hospital. The most significant independent risk factors were previous cesarean section, use of oxytocics, prolonged obstructed labor, and high parity. Younger age was found to be protective, while unbooked status was a major univariable risk factor. These findings emphasize the urgent need for targeted public health and clinical interventions to reduce the incidence of this catastrophic obstetric event.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To reduce the incidence of uterine rupture, we recommend:

- **Antenatal Care Access:** Enhance access to quality antenatal care, particularly in rural and underserved areas, focusing on health education and family planning to mitigate the risks associated with unbooked pregnancies and high parity.
- **Emergency Obstetric Care:** Strengthen the emergency obstetric referral system to ensure timely transfer of high-risk cases and immediate access to cesarean delivery for prolonged obstructed labor.
- **Oxytocin Protocols:** Implement and strictly enforce hospital protocols for the safe and appropriate use of oxytocic drugs for labor induction or augmentation.
- **Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs):** Engage with and train TBAs to recognize high-risk signs and avoid harmful interventions, facilitating timely referral to appropriate medical facilities.

LIMITATIONS

This study was conducted in a single tertiary hospital, which limits the generalizability of the findings. The retrospective nature of the study introduced potential limitations, including the risk of misclassification bias, missing or incomplete records, and potential selection bias despite efforts to mitigate it. Furthermore, residual confounding may exist, and the multivariable model may be subject to instability, necessitating cautious interpretation of the highly magnified Adjusted Odds Ratios.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Tiamiyu I.: Concept, drafting, and final preparation.

Ogbiti M.I.: Initial manuscript write-up.

Nwankwo C.C.: Proofreading and critical review.

Ezugwu O.P.: Data collection and curation.

Ojeh-Oziegbe O.G.: Statistical analysis and discussion.

Abubakar S.M., Dawúd R.M., Balogun S.A., Bathna D., Calvin C., Ibrahim H.I., Jaafaru U, Nakande JA, Abdulraheem M, Habibah HI : Data acquisition and secondary review.

All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

